

Demystifying Tales of Seasoned Teachers in 21st Century Milieu: A Phenomenological Inquiry

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Abstract. This study explored the lived experiences of seasoned teachers on the use of technology in the 21st-century milieu using qualitative phenomenological design. The study participants were the ten seasoned teachers in the Division of Davao City. Respectively, an in-depth interview was done, and thematic analysis was employed to gather the lived experiences of the participants. Data collection and data analysis were done simultaneously in this study. Adding to the first question on the lived experiences, three themes emerged: creating a well-managed classroom, fostering a positive classroom climate, and becoming innovative in teaching. Meanwhile, other themes emerged regarding the challenges and coping mechanisms of these seasoned teachers in integrating technology in the 21st-century milieu, such as inadequate knowledge and skills, unprepared teachers, and lack of facilities. Furthermore, in terms of the insights of seasoned teachers on technology use, three themes emerged: elevating motivation, strengthening ICT workshops, and providing ample facilities. Notably, the findings of this study plead that the Department provide the necessary facilities, workshops, and training to make them efficient and effective. On the other hand, the results revealed that teachers were pleading for ample facilities in each station; they also shared that ICT provides the flexibility and availability of learning materials that students can access even outside the classroom. The teaching-learning process became smoother and more straightforward when technology was integrated.

KEY WORDS

1. education 2. seasoned teachers 3. ICT workshops

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1. Introduction

The challenges that teachers face in the 21st century include keeping up with technological advancements, addressing students' diverse backgrounds and levels of preparation, creating relevant and meaningful curricula, balancing the need for assessment with fostering a love of learning, and finding time for collaboration and professional development. Teaching is the ability to assist learners in organizing, directing, and maximizing the stream of developing life experiences. Notably, the educational system has adapted paradigm shifts through 21st-century teaching-learning, where skill development has become a necessity and priority in delivering quality education to Filipino youth (Wayne, 2019). Thus, teaching has become very demanding, getting more complex, and challenging for the skills acquisition of teachers,

especially for the seasoned ones, learning resources, specifically the technology used inside the classroom (Boyer, 2020). However, the incapability of seasoned teachers to adapt to the trends in education and the lack of motivation regulation in learning and practicing the advent of technology in teaching has become a problem in the 21st-century milieu. In addition, seasoned teachers were still reluctant to integrate technology despite the new setup in education. It was evident that these teachers immediately sought help from whoever was willing and available (De Guzman, 2019). In Kenya, it has been reported that seasoned teachers are facing hurdles in the academe since the retention and patience of learners in learning have been decreasing because of the modern age competition, availability of alternate sources of knowledge like the internet, and social media which created domino effects in our educational system, (Canter, 2019). More so, in Laos, 70 percent of learners have access to smartphones, and 45 percent are online constantly, which leads them to be distracted in class during the subjects of seasoned teachers (Schlosser, 2018). In fact, a survey revealed that learners tend to refuse to attend classes because they engage in online gaming rather than listen to their traditional teacher (Boyer, 2020). Meanwhile, in the Philippines, teaching has been considered an immense challenge in their educational system because of the traditional lack of equipped, efficient, adaptive, and innovative teaching force, which might demotivate the learners (Green, 2015). In addition, a study revealed that 4 out of 10 Filipino seasoned teachers tend to be more traditional and that learners tend to believe that

learning is a simple and unsophisticated process (De Mesa, 2016). Furthermore, the University of the Philippines Diliman, Quezon City, conducted an International Conference on teaching pedagogy highlighting the importance of innovating teaching strategies and techniques for the holistic development of 21st-century learners, especially in this new everyday landscape (Guillermo, 2018). Meanwhile, a local setting survey through DepEd Onse revealed that 5 out of 10 seasoned teachers needed help in assimilating the new trends in education, especially if it required integrating technology in executing the lesson (Santos, 2020). There were also some hitches in coping with Generation Z learners as to what teaching pedagogy fits into them, for they were molded and developed in an external environment where the advent of technology is at its peak (De Guzman, 2019). Studies have been conducted on the advent of technology. However, fewer studies have been done on the lived experiences of seasoned teachers teaching Generation Z, specifically in this new typical landscape. Hence, there was an urgency to conduct this study since it could contribute to the academic society as this study will serve as a basis for crafting programs, seminar training, and workshops suited for seasoned teachers in the Department of Education. More so, this study will also provide training materials and activities that the teachers inside the classroom can use to develop and transform their teaching practices suited to the 21st-century era. Furthermore, this study is imperative since it allowed us to glimpse into the triumphs and hurdles of seasoned teachers amidst teaching in the 21st-century era.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This phenomenological study aimed to discover and understand the lived experiences of seasoned teachers on the use of technology in this new everyday landscape in the division of Davao City. Through their experiences, information was gathered to gain insights on becoming more effective and efficient in providing quality education to Filipino learners. Furthermore, it is crucial to investigate and find out the challenges and their coping mechanisms in integrating technology in a classroom setting.

1.2. *Research Questions*—This study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the lived experiences of seasoned teachers using technology in teaching in the 21st-century milieu?
- (2) What are the challenges, and how do the participants cope with the challenges encountered in using technology while teaching in a 21st-century milieu?
- (3) What are the educational management insights of seasoned teachers regarding the use of technology in teaching in the 21st-century milieu?

1.3. *Definition of Terms*—The following terms were conceptually and operationally defined for a clearer understanding of the study. Seasoned Teachers. The term was defined as mature teachers with field experience (Greenfield, 2016). This study pertained to teachers who have practiced the profession for twenty

years and who were still passionate about teaching in the 21st century. 21st-century Milieu. This term was defined as today's era and utilizing today's tools and technology (Bethel, 2019). In the context of this study, it refers to a generation in which the advent of technology was of great help, most especially in the teaching-learning process.

1.4. *Significant of the Study*—This research work is beneficial to the following entities: This study gave the Department of Education an idea of how to care for seasoned teachers still passionate about teaching. Furthermore, it also gave the department an idea of what programs, seminars, and platforms must be given to seasoned teachers to integrate technology into teaching. It enabled the school administrators and officials to consider some of these factors and give them perspectives on the valuable experiences of seasoned teachers. Thus, helping

them design a program that would increase the motivation of teachers in their work. This study allowed seasoned teachers to express their insights into adapting to the 21st-century milieu or this new ordinary landscape. It also broke the stereotype and proved that seasoned teachers could effectively and efficiently teach. This study was of great help for future researchers to understand the underlying adversities encountered by seasoned teachers in adapting 21st-century learning skills and students. They could use the data for further studies that are related to the topic they have identified.

1.5. *Theoretical Lens*—This study was gleaned from Perry and Weinstein's Adaptation Theory (1988), which posits that adaptation is defined as being able to adapt and adjust to the environment one has been embracing and experiencing. It has also been explained that humans can blend with their environment or surroundings. More so, as explained by (Garcia, 2013), adaptation is human beings' active modification of their behaviors to adjust to meet the requirements of a new environment. In the school setting, many factors likely influence successful

adaptation (Chan (2017). In the context of this study, adapting to the fast-changing learning environment and blending with the new era could somehow make a difference in the acquisition of students' learning. Therefore, seasoned teachers must be able to adapt to teaching practices for the active, effective, and efficient teaching-learning process (Maraat, 2019). This finding has been supported by the study (Santos, 2021), which posits that teachers in this new everyday landscape must learn about the advancement and trends in education for learners are becoming

ing techier and, thus, prefer to experience digital learning opportunities. Furthermore, this study was gleaned from Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977), which emphasizes the importance of observing and modeling the behaviors, attitudes, and emotional reactions of others to gain new knowledge and perspective. It also revealed that meaningful learning is possible through observation, imitation, and modeling, which means that various environmental factors highly influence most human behaviors and behavioral changes. In this study, this theory served as a springboard for understanding the importance of social learning. When seasoned teachers engaged in a new environment, they were able to learn new concepts and behaviors from external standards and eventually understand, create, and evaluate appropriate actions applicable in the new context, which could be in the form of adapting the new strategies and innovations from the millennial in order to blend with the 21st-century learners. Hence, if these teachers were exposed to the trends in 21st-century teaching, learners would become more active, creative, and critical thinkers. Furthermore, this study was also gleaned from the Experiential Learning Theory of David Kolb 1984, which explained that the concrete experience, reflected observation, abstract contextualization, and active experimentation from four process stages can transform into effective learning. In this study, this theory served as a basis for the importance of the experience and its reflection in the learning process for teachers and students. Furthermore, this theory explains that the reflection of the teachers through their experience allows them to process new learning

from experience. Thus, they can evaluate their learning. Moreover, this theory emphasizes how experiences, including cognition, provide these seasoned teachers the time and space to participate in learning by engaging in authentic, modern situations, Botic (2015). This study's story sheds light on how these seasoned teachers learned to manipulate, utilize, and integrate technology in their classes to make teaching-learning effective. This study also emphasized that seasoned teachers learned best when they experienced a real scenario. This would enable them to explore new learning and shift to the modern way of teaching utilizing the advent of technology. Thus, through experiential learning, hands-on activities, and reflection, seasoned teachers were able to assimilate new experiences. The teachers are facilitators of the learning. The focus of a 21st-century teacher is on students by developing higher-order thinking skills, effective communication, collaboration, and other skills that they need in the 21st century. The teachers must develop new teaching strategies that are radically different. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. As seen in the figure, there are three interconnected working themes. It presents a qualitative inquiry into the experiences of seasoned teachers using technology in teaching, the challenges and coping mechanisms of seasoned teachers using technology in teaching, and the insight drawn from the study's findings. These three interconnected working themes present the whole picture of teachers' experiences as they describe how they engage seasoned teachers using technology.

2. Methodology

This chapter includes the research design, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the study's trustworthiness, and the ethical considerations. This study utilized a qualitative phenomenological approach to demystify the lived experiences of seasoned teachers teaching in the 21st-century milieu. As mentioned (Zubel, 2016), qualitative research design is generally

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

defined as a method that delves into participants’ observations, experiences, thoughts, and feelings. It is used to understand underlying reasons, opinions, and motivations, uncover trends in thought and opinions, and dig deeper into the problem (Zapanta, 2015). In addition, Creswell (2013) stated that qualitative research is a method of exploring and understanding the individual or group of people who have experienced a situation or phenomenon. It is also the most common method used to gather data through interviews, which may be structured, semi-structured, or unstructured (Freeman, 2016). On the other hand, phenomenology is a qualitative research method used to describe how human beings experience a certain situation or phenomenon (Zimmer, 2012). It is also an approach to qualitative research focusing on the commonality of a group’s lived experiences. It is an inquiry from philosophy in which the researcher describes the lived experiences of individuals about the phenomenon (Wamar, 2014). Moreover, the phenomenological approach allows the researcher to delve into the perceptions, perspectives, understandings, and feelings of those who have experienced or lived the phenomenon (Labasantos, 2014). This approach’s fundamental goal was to describe the nature of a particular phenomenon, Creswell (2013). In the context of my study, the researcher utilized the qualitative research design to understand the lived experiences of seasoned teachers on their use of technology in teaching in the 21st-century milieu. Furthermore, phenomenological design is apt to use since a small group needs to collect data through their thoughts, opinions, or experiences. In addition, it sought to understand how people experienced a situation. It utilized open-ended interview guide questions to allow the participants to describe the experience from their point of view entirely. Hence, the participants’ feelings, responses, thoughts, and opinions were analyzed easily through this approach.

2.1. *Philosophical Assumptions—*

The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background for the conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types, which are elaborated below. Good Research involves selecting the topic, problem, or area of interest and the paradigm. Ontology. This part of the research includes defining the nature of reality even if the relevant phenomena are not observed. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by the study participants. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation, thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the realities of the seasoned teachers in teaching using technology in this era were explored, elaborated, and demystified. In this study, the researcher relied on the participants' voices and interpretations through the themes created from the data gathered. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. I ensured that the participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This assumption was based upon understanding the nature of knowledge; the researcher becomes immersed in the study and gets as close to the study participants as possible. In addition, it refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims were justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985), as cited by Creswell (2013), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an "insider." Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). In this study, the researcher utilized phenomenology with thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief." This research aimed to gather essential details on the experiences of seasoned teachers in using and integrating technology in teaching, particularly in Davao City. Furthermore, the researcher made sure to establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences of public school teachers as they attended multiple webinars to equip themselves with the knowledge and skills needed to deliver education in a new normal. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2013) explained that the role of values in a study is significant. It also suggests that the researcher must openly discuss the values that shape the narrative and include her interpretation in conjunction with the participants' interpretation. In this study, the researcher upheld the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. The researcher, therefore, preserved the merit of the participant's answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participant's interpretation. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using a personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the study context, the researcher used the first person to explain the experiences and coping mechanisms of the public school teachers and thoroughly discussed their responses during the interview.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology differed from the method, which was a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method referred to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the experiences and coping mechanisms of the seasoned teachers, specifically those from Davao City, were unleashed from their narratives. The researcher’s drive-in knowing the deeper meaning of the predicaments of the physical education teachers became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias (2013), considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena.” By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers so that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological

research was based on two premises; the first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs (2006), experience was a source of knowledge and shaped one’s behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research was that the everyday world was a valuable and productive source of knowledge, that we could learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which is concerned with the “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the subjective experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the public-school teachers were explored, and insights were drawn as the basis for the possible future researches and policy analysis with this research.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study used qualitative research employing phenomenology. Interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994). The data was then read, reread, and culled for phrases, and themes were grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this process, the researcher

constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. In this study, phenomenology attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher uses bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is memorizing (Maxwell, 2013).

2.4. *Research Participants*—The participants in this study were composed of ten (10) informants. The selected participants were public school teachers from the Davao City Division. All the participants were the public seasoned teachers from various nearby schools. They must be permanent and have taught for at least

two (20) years. All the participants came from the intermediate grade level, regardless of age, sex, and marital status. The research participants were selected and identified through snowball or chain sampling. Snowball sampling was a method in qualitative research in which one interviewee gives the researcher the name of at

least one more potential interviewee. That interviewee, in turn, could provide another name of at least one more potential interviewee, and so on, with the sample growing like a rolling snowball if more than one referral per interviewee is provided (Patton, 2002). Moreover, snowball sampling or chain-referral sampling was defined as a non-probability sampling technique in which the samples have rare traits (Bhat, 2018). In this study, I selected ten (10) participants, as suggested by Cresswell (2013) and cited by

Guetterman (2015), who underwent the interview. They were selected based on the criteria and identified explicitly as seasoned teachers who have practiced teaching in public schools for twenty years and above. However, they were identified as teachers having difficulties adapting and integrating technologies in classroom discussions and who tend to focus on the traditional ways of teaching. These teachers were willing to be interviewed.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Considering the nature of qualitative studies, the interaction between researchers and participants can be ethically challenging for the former, as they are personally involved in different stages of the study. Therefore, the formulation of specific ethical guidelines in this respect is essential. The relationship and intimacy established between the researchers and participants in qualitative studies could raise a range of ethical concerns, and qualitative researchers face dilemmas such as respect for privacy, the establishment of honest and open interactions, and avoiding misrepresentations. Richards and Schwartz (2002) emphasize that a fundamental ethical requirement of all research should be scientifically sound. The research must be appropriately designed and carried out by researchers with adequate expertise and supervision. It should be worth doing because the result generates tangible benefits. In addition, Sanjari (2014) stated that consent has been recognized as an integral part of ethics in research carried out in different fields. For qualitative researchers, it was of the utmost importance to specify in advance which data were collected and how they were used. He also stated that informed consent was a prerequisite for all research involving identifiable sub-

jects, except in cases where an ethics committee judges that such consent was not possible and where it was felt that the benefits of the research outweighed the potential harm. A minimum requirement for an interview study should be that written consent was obtained from the participant after they have been informed, verbally and in writing, about the following issues: the purpose and scope of the study, the types of questions that were likely to be asked, the use to which the results were put, the method of anonymization and the extent to which participants' utterances were used in reports. Participants should also be given time to consider their participation and ask the researcher questions. The researcher would follow ethical considerations in this study as part of the qualitative research process. The researcher was responsible for informing the participants about the different aspects of the research's incomprehensible language. The needed clarifications include the following issues: the nature of the study, the participants' potential role, the identity of the researcher, the objective of the research, and how the results were published and used. Similarly, this study was submitted to the ethics committee of Rizal Memorial College, a graduate school, for verification and approval.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—

The researcher plays multiple and dynamic roles in the research and is primarily responsible for the different tasks and obligations of the researcher (Green, 2013). The researcher was likely known to be an instrument who would prepare the interview guide questions, collaborate, interact with the participants, and gather data through interviews. Moreover, the researcher would transcribe, analyze, and ensure smooth proceedings in qualitative research (Denzin Lincoln, 2013). As Scott (2016) mentioned, the researcher identified the participants who would undergo in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. The researcher also acted as an interviewer and prepared the interview guide questions. In addition, the researcher encoded, transcribed and analyzed data (Celin, 2015). In the context of this study, the researcher identified the participants who un-

derwent the in-depth interview and the focus group discussion. The researcher also served as the interviewer, asking the participants questions to extract rich data. The researcher also served as the data collector, gathering ample data for the study. The researcher was also the data encoder, entering accurate data extracted from the interview. The researcher played a note-taker who wrote the essential points during the in-depth interview. Afterward, the researcher was the transcriber who transcribed the data from the in-depth interview using the audio recorder to record the conversation to gather data and extract essential information. As a transcriber, the researcher included all the verbatim responses and translated the participants' responses. Lastly, the researcher was the data analyst who analyzed and categorized the gathered data to generate themes.

2.7. Data Collection—In obtaining pertinent data, the researcher organized and followed a step-by-step procedure. Qualitative research engages a series of activities in collecting data before arriving after the study (Creswell, 2007). First was the site or individual; the participants were the seasoned public school teachers from the Davao City Division. Second was access and rapport. The graduate student was given a letter from the Dean of the Graduate School for the superintendent's approval. A permission letter for the school division Superintendent, Principal, and the concerned public school teachers was prepared for accessible data collection. The third was the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants experienced the phenomenon being studied. Ten (10) participants were selected in this study. The selected seasoned public school teachers were considered individuals who could best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and

could facilitate data collection. The fourth was the form of data collection; information was collected through the Virtual In-Depth Interview (IDI), primarily with the 10 participants. The fifth was the recording procedures. A protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures, and a predesigned form was used to record information collected during an observation or interview. The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last or seventh step was storing data; Davidson (1996) suggested using a database to back up information collected and note changes for all types of research studies. The data collection was conducted face-to-face with the participants. The researcher facilitated the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and in-depth Interview. The researcher ensured an ICF and asked permission from the superiors to conduct the study. Moreover, the participants also filled out the interview form provided to them and submitted it to the researcher.

2.8. Data Analysis—

After the data collection, the data gathered during the in-depth interview were transcribed, translated, and analyzed. In order to achieve the accurate and exact data needed in the study, an iterative process was followed in thematic analysis, which was the familiarization of the data, generating initial code, searching for themes, reviewing and refining the themes, and lastly, producing the report of the results, as this was the basis for generating the core ideas (Braune Clark, 2014). Thematic Content Analysis. Thematic analysis was a process of extracting themes. The transcripts were organized into core ideas; major themes were extracted, explained, and written under each topic. Relevant citations from the interviews were written in the results to support the themes found (Boyce, 2016). Similarly, thematic analysis was a flexible data analysis plan used in qualitative research to generate data from the interview, Beau (2018). It helps the researchers move from a broad data reading towards a specific research question. Meanwhile, data would remain private and confidential to ensure participants' identity. They would have their name coded, and after the transcription, participants were given copies of the transcripts to correct and verify answers in the interview (Boyce Neale, 2016). The coding system consisted of a list of codes hierarchically grouped and ordered according to the concept they were related to (Moral, Antonio, Ferre, Larra 2015). Thematic analysis and a coding system were also used to develop the synthesis themes. I categorize the participants' responses from specific to general to generate a set of comprehensive themes. Document analysis. Document analysis was a form of qualitative research that used a systematic procedure to analyze documentary evidence and answer specific research questions. Similar to

other methods of analysis in qualitative research, document analysis requires repeated review, examination, and interpretation of the data to gain meaning and empirical knowledge of the construct being studied. Document analysis could be conducted as a stand-alone study or as a component of a more extensive qualitative or mixed methods study, where it was often used to triangulate findings gathered from another data source, such as interview or focus group transcripts, observation, and surveys. When used in triangulation, documents could corroborate, refute, elucidate, or expand on findings across other data sources, which helps guard against bias (Frey, Bruce B., 2018). Triangulation of Data. Triangulation means using multiple methods to collect data on the same topic. This was a way of assuring the validity of research through various methods to collect data on the same topic, which involves different types of samples and data collection methods. However, the purpose of triangulation was not necessarily to cross-validate data but to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon (Kulkarni, Prashant, 2013). Environmental triangulation. Environmental triangulation was limited to studies where certain environmental factors could influence the findings. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors, such as the study's time, day, and season. The idea was to determine which of these factors influenced the information received, and these factors were then changed to see if the findings were the same. The validity could be established if the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suits the environment of the research being conducted.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—Braun and Clark (2006) state that the qualitative data analy-

sis methods fall into two groups. The first group consists of methods driven by an epistemologi-

cal or theoretical position, which have limited variability in how they are applied within their frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) and methods that are situated within a broad theoretical framework and can therefore be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks, such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA) narrative analysis (NA). The second group includes methods independent of theory and epistemology, which could be applied across various theoretical and epistemological approaches and are, therefore, very flexible. One such method is thematic analysis, which, through theoretical freedom, “provides flexible and valuable research tool, potentially providing a rich, detailed, yet complex account of data (Braun Clark, 2006). The researcher observed several steps in conducting a thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. The researcher relied on my resources to transcribe using my computer and some reliable headphones. The researcher spent several nights listening to the interviews to deepen my understanding of the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing to conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated the layout and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step was data extraction and analysis. As a researcher, I used manual techniques based on note-taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included verbatim recordings of selected spoken

words. The researcher selected quotations about central issues or when what was said seemed important or interesting. The researcher used several different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. The researcher marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. The researcher used thematic grids and charts, the framework technique developed by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al., 2003). This technique was helpful to me in coding, sorting, and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was instrumental in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedures included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross-referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. The researcher familiarized with the data by reading the whole data set and noting initial ideas. Phase 2. The researcher generated initial codes, which are the most essential segments of the raw data that can identify an exciting feature. Phase 3. The researcher searched for themes by sorting codes into potential themes and collating all data extracts within identified themes. Phase 4. The researcher reviewed the themes, refined them further (at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set), and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub-themes. Phase 5. The researcher defined and named themes, ensuring they gave the reader an immediate sense of the theme. Phase 6. The researcher wrote the report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes) and used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments about the research question.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study—*

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

The trustworthiness of qualitative research was the true value of the study's findings and the accuracy of data interpretations collected from the participants' experiences (Creswell, 2014). To ensure trustworthiness in my research, the researcher favorably considered four elements suggested by Shenton (2014) and Letts et al. (2017): credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. Credibility refers to whether the research findings represent a plausible and convincing conceptual interpretation and analysis of the data from the participants' original data (Creswell, 2014). In addition, credibility involves establishing the truth of the research findings. It means there was a need to show that the findings were accurate and honest. Furthermore, it was the quality of being believed or accepted as true, real, or honest. To address credibility issues, the researcher followed and established necessary procedures. In order to avoid biases in this study, the researcher ensured triangulation. As Miguel (2014) mentioned, triangulation ensures the validity of research by utilizing varied methods in collecting data. It also envisions capturing different dimensions of the same phenomenon. In addition, the researcher established prolonged engagement with the participants since the researcher's extended time in the field improved the respondents' trust and provided a greater understanding of the participants' culture and context (Onwuegbuzie Leech, 2007). In the context of this study, the researcher spent enough time learning and understanding the phenomenon, which involved observing the environment and speaking with a range of people who had experienced the phenomenon. In addition, it would help develop rapport and consider a genuine way to build trust. More so, iterative questioning was done. It refers to a systematic, repetitive, and recursive process in qualitative research that was vital in gathering and collecting rich, specific, useful information needed in the study. Thus, in this study, the researcher used interview guide questionnaires that were checked and validated by a panel of experts. In addition, during the interviews, the researcher asked follow-up questions to gather rich data. In addition, to ensure credibility, the researcher ensured that member checking was done after data collection since Lincoln and Guba (1985) stated that member checking is another method of ensuring credibility. It was defined as sharing a summary of findings or the whole findings with the participants. In the context of my study, the researcher provided the participants with a copy of the transcripts for them to correct, verify, and edit what they said during the in-depth interview. After that, the researcher asked them to sign the certification as proof that they had checked and approved the findings presented. Transferability was concerned with the extent to which the findings of one study can be applied to other situations. It was the degree to which the findings of this inquiry could be applied or transferred beyond the bounds of the project (Lincoln Guba, 2013). Transferability shows that the findings are applicable in the contexts (Bryne, 2013). This was supported by Lincoln and Guba (2013) and Firestone (2014), as cited by Shenton (2015), who suggested that it is the responsibility of the researcher to ensure that enough contextual information about the fieldwork sites is provided to enable the reader to transfer information. In order to have transferability, the researcher procured a detailed and thorough description of the methodology and the phenomenon being studied. Goodwin (2017) revealed that thick description was a technique in which the researcher provided a robust and detailed account of the participants' experiences during the data collection. Similarly, Lincoln and Guba (2013) describe thick description as a way of achieving a type of external validity. Hence, the researcher ensured the data were on file to make this study more credible and transferable. Dependability assesses the quality of the integrated data collection pro-

cesses, data analysis, and phenomenal explanation (Creswell, 2013). Also, dependability means that the findings are consistent and can be repeated (Cohen Crabtree, 2008). Thus, Lincoln and Guba (2013) stressed the close ties between credibility and dependability, arguing that, in practice, a demonstration of the former goes some distance in ensuring the latter. In order to address the dependability of this study, I would report all the processes within the study in detail to enable future researchers to have further studies relevant to my work, if not necessarily to gain the same results. Also, the researcher carefully employed data-gathering procedures during the in-depth interviews using an interview guide questionnaire, which experts validated. Above all, to check this study's dependability, I would ensure that the data analyst checked the generated themes and core ideas and reviewed the analysis, conceptualization, and interpretation of the findings. Confirmability measures how well the data collected supports the inquiry's findings (Creswell, 2014). Also, it was considered as the degree of neutrality, in which the findings of a study are shaped by the research participants instead of the researcher's bias, motivation, or interest (Miles et al., 2013). Moreover, a detailed methodological description lets the reader determine how far the data might be accepted. Critical to this process is the audit trail, which allows any observer to trace the course of the research step-by-step via the decisions made and procedures described as suggested by (Guba and Lincoln, 2013). In addition, the audit trail was an in-depth approach that illustrated that the findings were based on participants' narratives and involved describing how the researcher collected and transparently analyzed the data. It was indeed a way to show that the analysis follows a logical path based on participant's narratives and responses. In the context of my study, I would incorporate an audit trail to analyze the data gathered quickly. I would also incorporate details of the data collection process, data analysis, and interpretation here. At the same time, it was easier for me to track the participants' responses, report, and explain everything that I did so that it would be easier for the data analyst to analyze the data being gathered.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the study's results and discussion. It also includes the participants' responses, which the researcher analyzed thoroughly and eventually extracted the core ideas. Based on the core ideas, the themes emerged. The presentation of the results and the data resulting from the interviews were analyzed, organized, and categorized based on the sequence of research interview guide questions.

3.1. The Lived Experiences of Seasoned Teachers in using technology in 21st century milieu—On the first question, the seasoned teachers shared their experiences using technology in class. After the interview, transcription, and careful analysis of the documented data, the following themes emerged: Creating a well-managed classroom, Fostering a Positive Classroom Climate, and Becoming Innovative in Teaching. The seasoned teachers provided the researcher with all their exciting experiences during the interview.

3.1.1. They are creating a well-managed classroom—As revealed by seasoned teachers integrating technology in their classes, technology can create a positive and well-managed classroom. Based on the participants' experiences, using technology during discussions

and other activities makes learners behave and participate in class. Thus, it creates a positive impact on learners' behavior. The survey done by Deped Onse also supports this finding; 54 percent of the teachers responded that utilizing technology in teaching promotes great learning and enables learners to become active and motivated in class. Cruz (2022) revealed that learning becomes better when technology is integrated, especially for Generation Z. In addi-

3.1.2. Fostering Positive Classroom Climate—One of the experiences revealed by the seasoned teachers in utilizing technology in class is that it creates a positive classroom climate. Based on the participants' narratives, they revealed that integrating technology in class provides numerous advantages on their part. They also revealed that seasoned teachers are very blessed and thankful because, at the same time, it is also a new learning for them to discover new online applications that they can use for their classes. They also revealed that students responded positively when seasoned teachers utilized technology in class. Similarly, this result on the positive impact of integrating technology in class is congruent with the finding elucidating that having a positive classroom climate is very important since it promotes the

3.1.3. Becoming Innovative in Teaching—The seasoned teachers also revealed that using technology in class enabled teachers to become innovative. The participants also shared that technology provides a new path to becoming an innovative teacher. They also shared that some seasoned teachers need yearly training, seminars, and workshops to enhance their learning. Moreover, seasoned teachers have shared that teaching in this era has become easier with the advent of technology. This finding has also been supported by Chandler's (2017) study, which emphasized that 32 percent of teachers enjoy

tion, when technology is integrated into class, learners become very active; they are thrilled to discover new lessons, Patt (2016). In the same nutshell, this finding is supported by the survey results done by the Department of Education, which revealed that 13 percent of teachers said that class becomes well-managed and active when using technology in class (De Guzman, 2016).

smooth flow of transferring learning (Steeve, 2017). Meanwhile, some strategies teachers can use to set up the classroom include creating a positive classroom climate, engaging students in bonding activities to help them become more comfortable with each other, establishing rules and expectations, practicing routines, and developing logical consequences if students do not follow the rules, (Collier, 2017). In addition, Smith (2015) suggests that seasoned teachers can teach social skills by modeling appropriate social interactions, giving students time to develop and practice group and social skills, and demonstrating self-control and stress management techniques. Wright (2014) has documented that the teacher is the most important factor affecting student learning. He added that the quality of an educational system depends upon the quality of teachers who operate it.

various online applications that enable them to become innovative in their teaching. In addition, using different online platforms, students become more active and engaging in the lesson, Greg (2017). Meanwhile, it has been emphasized that student learning must go beyond mastery of core subjects and include 21st-century knowledge and skills like critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and technology literacy (Horn, 2015). They believe that new teacher candidates must be equipped with these 21st-century knowledge and skills and learn how to integrate them into classroom practice specif-

Fig. 3. Experiences of Seasoned Teachers in Integrating Technology

ically for the nation to realize its goal of successfully meeting the challenges of this century. In addition, Wagner (2016) said that seasoned teachers must be innovative in teaching millennial learners. He added that the integration of technology and using online applications is imperative. Teachers must employ active activities and work with students whose entire lives are immersed in the 21st-century media culture. Moreover, he explained that today's students are digital learners because they literally take in the world via the filter of computing devices: cellular phones, handheld gaming devices, and laptops they take everywhere in addition to computers, TVs, and game consoles (Green, 2018). However, Stark (2017) revealed in the study that most seasoned teachers utilize a traditional teaching approach, which results in less interaction. In addition, the traditional

approach to teaching fails to provide knowledge. Transfer and transfer of power from the teacher to the students, and the students cannot move the knowledge they have acquired in the school outside the classroom (Clark, 2016). Figure 3 shows the experiences of seasoned teachers in integrating technology. The emerging three themes are becoming innovative in teaching, creating a well-managed class, and fostering a positive classroom climate. Moreover, traditional approaches cannot create a link between the syllabi, the real world, and learning (Greg, 2015). Furthermore, data revealed that technology empowers teachers to develop creative and interactive classrooms and gives them access to innovative resources. Effective educators understand the benefits of integrating technology in the classroom and finding new ways to make lessons meaningful.

3.2. *The challenges and coping mechanism technology in class*—The seasoned public-school teachers revealed that they had encountered numerous difficulties when integrating technology into their classes. They also re-

vealed that upon integrating technology in classes, they had some coping mechanisms that they had used to cope with the challenges of integrating or utilizing technology in class. According to the participants, these are the prob-

lems that need to be solved by the Department; they also revealed that teachers need ample support to cope with these challenges. Here are some of the identified themes that emerged from the participants' narratives.

3.2.1. Inadequate Knowledge and Skills— As revealed, most seasoned teachers admitted that they lack ample knowledge and skills in manipulating their laptops or computers, which hinders them from integrating technology into their classes. They also shared during the interview that because of the lack of knowledge and skills, they tend to use traditional ways of teaching. Furthermore, as revealed by the participants, they needed more training, seminars, and workshops to gain more knowledge and experience. According to the findings of Jardin (2020), 34 percent of seasoned teachers in the Department of Education must undergo training, workshops, and seminars to blend with the new teaching modality, particularly the online class. Furthermore, in her survey, Tayamora (2021) revealed that 20 percent of the senior teachers do not own a laptop or a computer unit, which made them reluctant to integrate technology into their classes. This finding has also been supported by the findings of De Guzman (2020), which revealed that teachers' lack of knowledge and skills caused demotivation of the learners in their classes. Furthermore, inadequate knowledge and skills can affect a teacher's performance. It has been revealed that inadequately trained employees are likely to experience poor job performance and increased levels of work-related stress, Sanchez (2021). In addition, a lack of knowledge and skills can likely make teachers unhappy at work. It has also been revealed in the study of Jardin (2020) that poorly trained teachers are likely to feel undervalued, which will reduce productivity in the classroom setting. Moreover, this finding has been supported by De Guzman (2020), who emphasized that teachers must be given significant value regarding knowledge and skills acquisition in technological literacy.

3.2.2. Unprepared Teachers— According to the participants, one of the challenges they had encountered was the lack of preparation, time constraints, and unexpected situations, which hindered them from successfully utilizing technology in their discussions. Furthermore, they also shared that they needed more guidance and assistance from other teachers to make their presentations more effective and efficient. According to Johnson (2018), preparation and planning are crucial to the success of the teaching and learning process. He also mentioned that teachers must be prepared to deliver lessons and in a continuous state of planning and preparation. Meanwhile, as revealed in the survey of Catalan (2021), 3 out of 5 teachers attested that they are not prepared to apply technology in their class; thus, they tend to apply the traditional paper and pencil test. As Blake (2017) expressed, when teachers are not given ample access to professional development effective training, and exposure to learning communities, it might defeat the teacher's effectiveness, sense of purpose, and career advancement. Moreover, it has also been revealed that most teachers, at least 23 percent surveyed by the OECD, said they are not well prepared to use technology in the classroom. This finding is supported by the study by Sanchez (2020) that 18 percent of the teachers reported a higher need for professional development in ICT skills to blend with the transition to the new learning modality and faced great challenges in delivering quality instructions in an online setting. Thus, it has been

suggested that teachers must be prepared and give importance to acquiring knowledge and skills to apply technology in their respective classes (Blas, 2021).

3.2.3. Lack of Facilities—Another challenge that the seasoned teachers encountered was the lack of facilities. Based on their narratives, it is a need for the department to support and supply sufficient gadgets that the teachers could use in integrating technology in class. Furthermore, they also shared that some teachers are not familiar with the tools and applications on the computer or laptop because of insufficient facilities. Similarly, most seasoned teachers shared that they were unfamiliar with the installation and how to manipulate their gadgets. Seasoned teachers in far-flung areas pleaded to undergo workshops on information technology integration. One of the challenges mentioned by the participants of this study was the lack of facilities. It has been revealed that the lack of facilities hinders them from quality education in this new everyday landscape. Green's findings (2017) revealed that lacking facilities hurts teachers' job satisfaction, performance, and motivation. This is also supported by the study by Steeve (2019), which emphasized that 32 percent of the teachers responded that they are more motivated to teach when provided with ample support through a complete facility. Another 45 percent of teachers revealed that ample facilities make work efficient and effective. However, in far-flung areas, teachers cannot utilize the said technology because of the lack of power sources and the availability of the materials, and they would stick to the traditional way of delivering the lesson. According to Silvana (2016), students learn most when exposed to the traditional way of teaching because, in this way of teaching, students are organized and disciplined. On the other hand, many believe that the use of hi-tech mechanization hinders the steps of learning might transform learners into inefficient learners, which is considered an immense challenge for teachers (Wilfred, 2017). According to Velasco (2015), exposing learners to social platforms could be a significant source of distraction. He explained that statistics revealed that almost 60 of the students are exposed to social networking sites that rule their world, which might create a considerable distance, an immense gap between the learners and education. However, it is in the hands of the teachers to learn how to use the technology appropriately and productively. In addition, based on the findings of (Ramos, 2015), technology could change the perspective of everyone in terms of teaching. He further added that teaching with the use of technology enables the teacher to become innovative and systematic. Figure 4 shows the Challenges encountered by seasoned teachers in integrating technology. The emerging three themes are lack of facilities, unprepared teachers, and inadequate knowledge and skills.

3.3. Insights of seasoned teachers in integrating technology in 21st century milieu—The seasoned public school teachers shared their insights, hopes, and perceptions upon integrating technology into their classes. They also revealed that technology can be of great help to both students and teachers. Based on the data gathered teachers are also hoping and pleading for the Department of Education to provide enough facilities for teachers to use, as well as reliable and strong internet connectivity. Furthermore, they also hope these could be another venue for new skill development through providing workshops for teachers. In this question, three themes emerged: elevating motivation, strengthening ICT workshops, and providing ample facilities.

Fig. 4. Challenges of Seasoned Teachers in Integrating Technology

3.3.1. *Elevates Motivation*—According to the participants, integrating technology in class has many advantages. One of its advantages is that it is a strong source of motivation for both learners and teachers. In addition, they shared that students become more active and motivated when teachers use technology in discussing their lessons. This finding is also supported by the study of Morre (2014), which highlighted that 6 out of 10 learners prefer to attend their classes when teachers are utilizing technology in their discussions. In addition,

this is also supported by the findings of Camon (2015), which revealed that in Calabarzon, 35 percent of the teachers are equipped with the new trends in ICT integration; thus, learners are very active and participative in their classes. Moreover, as revealed in the study of De la Paz (2016), 4 out of 10 learners in Quezon City National High School tend to skip their classes when their teachers are still engaging in the traditional way of teaching. Thus, integrating technology in class is very important and of great help to both learners and teachers since it will attract motivation.

3.3.2. *Strengthening ICT Workshop*—One theme that emerged from the participants' insights and perceptions is strengthening the ICT workshop. Some of the seasoned teachers shared that it would be very nice if the Department of Education strengthened the workshops, training, and seminars so that teachers would become fully equipped with the necessary skills to integrate technology during discussions. This

finding also conforms to the study of Santos (2015), which revealed that 4 out of 10 seasoned teachers in the Department of Education need a refresher course in ICT integration. He added that these teachers tend to stick to the traditional way of teaching. As revealed by the survey of Deped Onse, 15 percent of the teachers in the Davao Region suggested that they needed additional training for ICT integration. Based on the study done by the Department of Education.

Fig. 5. Insights of Seasoned Teachers on ICT Integration

3.3.3. *Provision of ample facilities*—One of the themes that emerged from the experiences of the seasoned teachers is that there should be ample facilities in every school. Based on the results, seasoned teachers still hope the education department supplies and releases laptops for every teacher. They also added that it would be easier for each classroom to have robust internet connectivity to search for more online activities during discussions. This finding also conforms to Sanchez’s (2017) study, which states that every school must have proper facilities management. It is also supported by the study, which states that Proper management of facilities motivates employees, ensures you meet health and safety standards, ensures that all assets are in good condition, and helps the company focus better on their area of expertise, Cruz (2016). Furthermore, it is necessary to ensure the facility is properly managed for a company’s long-term growth, increasing productivity and ensuring cost-efficiency in operations. It is not just for ensuring the smooth running of day-to-day operations but is also es-

sential in the long run (Miguel, 2016). Figure 5 shows the Insights of seasoned teachers in integrating technology. The three themes are the provision of ample facilities, elevating Motivation, and strengthening the ICT workshop. The facility is properly managed for a company’s long-term growth, increasing productivity and ensuring cost-efficiency in operations. It is not just for ensuring the smooth running of day-to-day operations but is also important in the long run (Miguel, 2016). Based on the findings, seasoned teachers hope and pray that their schools will provide sufficient and updated facilities for a better teaching-learning process. This finding also conforms with the concept that having good facilities in schools helps improve environmental conditions (Barri, 2015). Furthermore, school facilities improve the quality of the study environment in the school, thus improving the quality of education. For example, if the classroom layout considers the room’s acoustics, then the students can focus and concentrate more on their studies, and teachers will face fewer distractions (Lim, 2018).

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the study's summary is presented. From the summary of the findings, I drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of this study was to find out the experiences, challenges, and insights of seasoned teachers as they integrate technology in the 21st-century milieu, specifically in the Davao region. Furthermore, this study would serve as a blueprint for what programs, seminars, training, and workshops must be given to seasoned teachers to teach the curriculum effectively and efficiently. To achieve the research objectives, I used a qualitative phenomenological method with thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines, I used open-ended interview questions to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored, which were the narratives of seasoned teachers upon integrating technology into their discussions.

4.1. Findings—After a thorough analysis of the data, the following themes emerged. On the first question, the lived experiences of the seasoned teachers on using technology, three themes emerged: Creating a well-managed classroom, fostering a positive classroom climate, and becoming innovative in teaching. Meanwhile, the second grand tour question on the challenges encountered by these teachers in integrating technology revealed the following themes: Inadequate knowledge and skills, unprepared teachers, and the lack of facilities. Furthermore, on the last question about the insights and perceptions of seasoned teachers, the following themes emerged: increased motivation, strengthening ICT workshops, and provision of ample facilities.

4.2. Implications—The results of the analysis revealed the following significant findings: The seasoned teachers revealed that integrating technology in class significantly provides numerous advantages to the teaching-learning process. There has been a revelation that integrating technology during discussions can provide numerous advantages. Furthermore, data revealed that technology empowers teachers to develop creative and interactive classrooms and gives them access to innovative resources. Effective educators understand the benefits of integrating technology in the classroom and finding new ways to make lessons meaningful. Furthermore, it has also been revealed that integrating technology in class enabled them to foster a positive climate and become innovative in teaching. In fact. There has been a strong connection and mutual understanding regarding the teaching-learning process. One of the most important aspects of a teacher's and student's success is how well they can connect with each other. Teachers constantly sought ways to connect with their students and one another to build community in their courses. Technology allows teachers to connect with their students in a new way. It allows open lines of communication and uses the Internet to explain curriculum material in a new way, which can be very helpful to students. Since the result of the study has a positive impact on the teaching-learning process, integrating technology in class must be enhanced, improved, and elevated. Meanwhile, on the challenges seasoned teachers encountered by the seasoned teachers, results revealed that they needed adequate knowledge and skills to become innovative inside the classroom. Further, the department must focus on providing workshops on ICT integration. It was further revealed that adequate knowledge and skills in-

crease the confidence and productivity of the teachers. Similarly, it also improves engagement and retention. Thus, this must be given importance by the department. On the other hand, the results revealed that teachers were pleading for ample facilities in each station; they also shared that ICT provides the flexibility and availability of learning materials that students can access even outside the classroom.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the study's findings, they needed to be properly relayed and used by the significant people for whom this research was intended. Seasoned teachers. This study might help them be heard regarding their experience integrating technology in class. This study was a realization, tool, and awareness for the Department of Education on what they should focus on for the betterment of every school. This study allowed seasoned teachers to express their insights into adapting to the 21st-century milieu or this new normal landscape. It also broke the stereotype and proved that seasoned teachers can do effectively and efficiently in teaching. The school principals or school heads. It enabled the school administrators and officials to investigate some considerations and give them perspectives on the valuable experiences of seasoned teachers. Thus helping them design a program that would increase teachers' motivation in their work. Further, this study might reference the school head or principals on what must be given and provided to the teachers, especially the seasoned teachers. School heads may encourage teachers to share insight, knowledge, and skills through LAC sessions and another workshop. Department of Education. This study gave the Department of Education an idea of caring for seasoned teachers who are still passionate about

As added, teachers can also create and innovate interactive activities and lessons off-screen using ICT. The teaching-learning process became smoother and more straightforward when technology was integrated. Since the results revealed a lack of facilities, the Department of Education must allocate funds and focus on upgrading ICT facilities.

teaching. Furthermore, it also gave the department an idea of what programs, seminars, and platforms must be given to seasoned teachers to integrate technology into teaching. This study might be a reference for them to provide the needs of the teachers and the school. In addition, the department may provide more training, seminars, and workshops for seasoned teachers to enhance their skills in integrating technology in class to make them more effective and efficient. Thus providing learners with quality education. Other stakeholders. Stakeholders may help the school by extending a helping hand in improving the school structures and physical facilities. They are a great support in every school activity; in fact, they are considered as the parties who are interested in the school's success. They had the power to support and influence the school community. It would be of great help to future researchers to know the underlying adversities encountered by seasoned teachers in adapting 21st-century learning skills and students. They can use the data for further studies that are related to the topic they have identified. They may conduct the same study in a different location and context. They may also continue to study seasoned teachers, focusing on other aspects. In addition, this study could be a source for a study related to seasoned teachers and ICT integration.

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